

THE EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE LOCAL DEFORMATION AND DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF MMCS

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SUMMARY: Local deformation and damage analyses of a particulate reinforced 6061 aluminum alloy were performed. The matrix was under-aged and had a fraction of 20 vol pct SiC particles with a mean diameter of 100 μm . In-situ tensile tests were conducted to study the behavior of the composite quantitatively by the means automatic local deformation analyses. Local strains were found to be up to one order of magnitude higher than the global strain. The formation of deformation bands and the damage evolution around individual particles are analyzed. The dominant damage mechanism is particle fracture. Particle-matrix decohesion occurred rarely.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, composite architecture, digital image analysis, local deformation behavior, local fracture behavior

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this investigation is to improve the understanding of mechanisms that cause the poor ductility and fracture toughness of particulate reinforced Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs), see, e.g., [1-4]. In order to get detailed information about the deformation, damage evolution and fracture behavior, we investigate these phenomena locally. Individual regions on the surface of MMC specimens are investigated by in-situ deformation experiments in the scanning electron microscope (SEM).

The investigations are based on SEM images that are captured at different stages of deformation. By the means of a digital image analyses system, it is possible to calculate in-plane deformation maps. This method was developed by Davidson [1], who also performed first investigations on MMCs [2, 3]. We apply a new analysis system that provides a better accuracy and a higher lateral resolution [4, 5].

The development of strain localization and damage evolution by particle fracture and particle/matrix decohesion are monitored and studied in detail.

2. MATERIAL AND SPECIMENS

The investigated material is a powder-metallurgically processed MMC with an Al-6061 matrix and a fraction of 20 vol.% SiC particles with a mean diameter of 100 μm . The matrix grain size is approximately 5 μm .

Specimens were cut perpendicularly to the extrusion axis of the material. The tensile specimens have a cross section of 2 x 2 mm and a gauge length of 8 mm. The heat treatment was carried out after the machining of the specimens. The material was solution annealed at 530 °C for one hour, quenched in water (20 °C), and aged at 175 °C for 15 minutes, which corresponds to an under-aged condition. In this condition, the yield strength of the composite is $\sigma_{0.2} = 210$ MPa and the ultimate tensile strength $\sigma_u = 219$ MPa. The samples were mechanically polished and chemically etched in order to achieve an appropriate surface structure, which is necessary to apply the local deformation measurements [4, 5].

3. EXPERIMENTAL

An in-situ tensile test is carried out in the SEM. The specimen is loaded in discrete steps. At each step, stress and strain data is recorded and SEM-micrographs are taken. The global strain is measured with the help of SEM micrographs taken at low magnification and determining an average value of the deformation in the loading direction. The micrograph in Figure 1 shows the region where the local deformations are analyzed. The images have a resolution of 4000 x 3200 pixel, which corresponds to an area of about 900 x 720 μm . The loading direction is horizontally orientated (x).

Figure 1. SEM micrographs of the undeformed specimen (a) and the fractured specimen (b). The loading direction is parallel to the horizontal axis. The arrows indicate pre-damaged particles.

The automatic local deformation analysis is based on the automatic detection of homologue points in two micrographs taken at different loading stages. Homologue points are points in the images that belong to the same physical point on the specimen. The homologue points can be detected with an accuracy of approximately 0.05 pixel [4]. The density of the homologue points lies between 2 and 4 points per 100 pixel, i.e., 240.000 to 500.000 homologue points are found in each micrograph.

From each pair of homologue points, a displacement vector can be calculated. From the smoothed displacement field, the in-plane strain field can be derived. The procedure is described in [4, 5]. Two kinds of strain maps, cumulative and incremental strain maps, can be generated. Cumulative strain maps show the local strains between the undeformed specimen and the actual state; incremental strain maps show the strain increments of a considered deformation step. The strain accuracy depends on the density of homologue points, the smoothing procedure, and the magnification of the micrographs [4]; for the current deformation maps, the strain accuracy was about 0.005 at a lateral resolution of 4.5 μm . Due to the high Young's modulus of the SiC particles, the strains in the reinforcements are below the measurement accuracy.

4. RESULTS

4.1 LOCAL DISPLACEMENT PROFILES AND STRAIN FIELDS

Figure 2 shows a collection of strain maps of the region depicted in Figure 1a. Presented are the strains in tensile direction (ϵ_{xx}). The maps on the left-hand side are cumulative strain maps showing local strains at 0.25, 0.33, 0.56, and 1.10% global strain. The maps on the right-hand side are incremental strain maps between these steps (between 0.33 and 0.56% global strain, etc.).

Between 0 and 0.25% global strain, deformation occurs mainly at pre-damaged particles (7, 13 and 16, Fig 2a). Some small areas near particles appear also to be strained (e.g., left of 8 and 19, right of 15). By further deformation (0.25 – 0.33%), the pre-damaged Particles 13 and 16 get connected by a deformation band (Fig. 2b). The strains at Particles 8, 15 and 19 get higher (Fig. 2c). With ongoing loading of the specimen (0.33 – 0.56%), Particle 5 fractures and the region above of the particle shows a large deformation (Fig. 2d). New shearbands form in the matrix at angles of about 45° to the loading direction. These bands often cause high strains at particle edges. Note that the 13-16-deformation band becomes inactive in this loading step. The next deformation step (0.56 – 1.1%) ends up with various broken particles (Fig. 2f). For instance, Particle 1 cracks near the left interface. The top edge of Particle 2 breaks apart. Particle 6 fractures and a strong deformation band connects it with Particle 16 via the broken Particle 17. In the other direction from the crack at Particle 6, a deformation band leads to the cracked Particle 2. In the lower-right region of the analyzed area, the interface at Particle 15 breaks, and Particles 9 and 10 fracture. A strong deformation band connects these failure sites, final fracture occurs along this band. The final fracture of the specimen occurs at about 2.3% global strain, but it was not possible to take a high-resolution picture at this stage of deformation. The analysis of the standard-resolution images (1042x768 pixel) showed that the strain increased preferably on the right-hand side of the analyzed area, where finally the crack formed involving Particles 9, 10, 14 and 15. Particles 14 and 18 fractured between 1.1 and 2.3%, Particles 4,8 and others are found to be fractured on the broken specimen (cf. Figure 1b).

It is remarkable that at the deformation state of 0.56% there are still areas of very low strain, for example, below Particle 6. In order to get detailed information of the local deformation behavior, it is possible to extract displacement profiles from the deformation field along arbitrary lines. Figure 3a shows displacements (u_x) in tensile direction along the profile 1 depicted in Fig.1a. The strain, ϵ_{xx} , is then given by the gradient of the displacement curve. In the diagram particle positions are indicated by dashed vertical lines. The areas inside the particles are marked gray. It can be seen that Particle 5 fractures between 0.33 and 0.56% global strain and that the fracture of Particle 6 occurs between 0.56 and 1.10% global strain. Figure 3b shows a local displacement curve along profile 2 somewhat below Particle 6 (cf. Fig.1a). It can be seen that the local strain ϵ_L beneath particle 6 is only about 0.1%, whereas the average strain in the surrounding ϵ_S is about 0.5%. Therefore, Particle 6 must experience a high stress. After the fracture of Particle 6, the average strain in this area rises up to $\epsilon_S= 1.2\%$, which is nearly equal to the global strain. The local strain rises, due to the crack, to $\epsilon_L= 4.3\%$ (see also Fig. 5).

4.2 DAMAGE MECHANISMS

The analyzed area contains 56 particles. Nine particles are already pre-damaged before any loading is applied. In Table 1, the numbers of cracked particles are listed for every deformation stage. The predominant damage mechanism is particle fracture. Almost all of the particle-cracks are oriented perpendicular to the tensile axis and the cracks open in tensile direction, no shearing of the fragments of the broken particles is observed. After the final fracture of the specimen, the fraction of broken particles in the analyzed area of the failed specimen is about 54%. Compared to experiments carried out with materials reinforced with particles of a mean diameter of 10 μm , this value is much higher. This is in agreement with [6], where the fraction of broken particles is predicted to be higher for large reinforcement diameters. Matrix-particle decohesion occurs only at two particles.

Figure 2. Local strain maps of the region depicted in Figure 1a at different global strains (ϵ_{global}). Plotted are the strains (ϵ_{xx}) in the (horizontal) loading direction.

(a, c, e and g) are cumulative strain maps, (b, d and f) incremental strain maps.

Units are pixels, pixel-size = 0.226 μm .

- | | |
|---|--|
| (a)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 0.25% | (b)... ϵ_{global} 0.25 – 0.33% |
| (c)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 0.33% | (d)... ϵ_{global} 0.33 – 0.56% |
| (e)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 0.56% | (f)... ϵ_{global} 0.56 – 1.10% |
| (g)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 1.10% | |

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- | | |
|---|--|
| (a)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 0.25% | (b)... ϵ_{global} 0.25 – 0.33% |
| (c)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 0.33% | (d)... ϵ_{global} 0.33 – 0.56% |
| (e)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 0.56% | (f)... ϵ_{global} 0.56 – 1.10% |
| (g)... ϵ_{global} 0.0 – 1.10% | |

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Displacements in loading direction (u_x) at different global strains along the profiles indicated in Figure 1a; ϵ_L are local strains, ϵ_S strains in the surrounding of the local area (dash-dotted lines). Pixel-size = 0.226 μm .

Table 1: Particle Fracture

ϵ_{global}	σ_{global}	Cracked particles	Cracked particles	Decohesion
[-]	[MPa]	[-]	[%]	[-]
0.0	0.0	9	16.1	0
0.25	180.7	9	16.1	0
0.33	204.7	9	16.1	0
0.56	215.1	12	21.4	0
1.1	219.3	20	35.7	2
2.3	217.2	25	44.6	2
fractured	-	30	53.6	2

Figure 4 shows three of the fractured particles. Particle 5 fractures, but there is no crack propagation into the matrix. Only a blunted area forms in the matrix close to the particle-crack. The crack opening displacement (COD) is about $3.5\mu\text{m}$. On the contrary, the crack in Particle 6 propagates quickly after the cracking into the matrix material below the particle. On the upper side of the particle, the crack does not grow, see Fig. 5b. The COD in this case is about $0.9\mu\text{m}$ right after particle fracture, and rises to $5.9\mu\text{m}$ in the fractured specimen. The crack tip at the upper side still remains blunted. The crack at particle 17 grows into the matrix right after fracture, too. Also in this case, crack growth occurs only at one side, with a final COD of $4.9\mu\text{m}$. Note that the crack is deflected at the particle above Particle 17 (Fig. 4c). In order to find the reason for the crack growth at this low COD values, Particles 6 and 17 were investigated by stereoscopic images. It is found that the faces (lower side of 6 and upper side of 17), which go into the bulk, show very flat angles to the specimen surface. This aspect of the three-dimensional shape of the reinforcement is obviously the reason for the observed crack growth. It has to be mentioned that crack growth into the matrix was observed very rarely compared to the number of fractured particles.

Figure 5 shows the region around Particle 6 at the deformation stages before and after particle fracture (0.56 and 1.10% global strain). At 0.56%, the strains below Particle 6 are very low (cf. Section 4.1). Strains up to 0.75% are measured at the upper left side of the particle and its lower-right corner. Strong deformation occurs in the area around the pre-damaged Particle 7. After the fracture of Particle 6, a strong deformation band develops below Particle 3, which connects, in a zig-zag mode to a parallel deformation band through the initially broken Particle 17 (cf. Fig.2f). In the opposite direction, this deformation band causes the fracture of Particle 2. The average strain in the deformation band reaches about (3-4)%. The strains in the surrounding have also increased significantly (cf. also Fig. 1,2 and 3).

Matrix-particle decohesion and void formation/growth occurred very rarely. Figure 6 shows an example of an area with two decohesion sites and void growth. Matrix strains up to 8% are measured at a global strain of 1.1% (Fig. 6d). This is the path along which, at 2.3% global strain, final fracture occurs (Fig. 1b).

Figure 4. The cracks at Particles 5 (a), 6 (b) and 17 (c) after the fracture of the specimen. Note the crack deflection in (c) at the particle above Particle 17.

Figure 5. The local region around Particle 6. (a) at a global strain of 0.56%, (b) at 1.10%. (c) and (d) cumulative strain maps corresponding to these two deformation stages. The arrows indicate particle cracks. Pixel-size = 0.226 μ m.

Figure 6. The local region near Particle 15. (a) at a global strain of 0.0%, (b) at 1.10%. (c) and (d) cumulative strain maps corresponding to the deformation stages at 0.56% and 1.10% global strain. Note that the voids at 1.10% are about two times larger than in the undeformed state. Along this strong deformation band final fracture of the specimen occurs involving the sites of decohesion, void growth and the particle crack. Pixel-size = 0.226 μ m.

The fracture surfaces of two particles in the analyzed area were investigated in order to find the sites of the fracture origin. This is important to see whether the particles fractured due to failures on the surface, which might be caused by the surface preparation. Figure 7 shows the fracture surfaces of Particles 10 and 14 (cf. Fig. 1). On the fracture surface of Particle 10, river-patterns lead from the fracture origin towards the specimen surface. The shape of Particle 10 below the specimen surface (Fig. 7a) is the explanation for the low strains between Particle 10 and 15 in the local strain map (cf. Fig.2). Also in the case of Particle 14, it can be seen clearly that the origin of the crack is not on the specimen surface.

Figure 7. Fracture surfaces of broken particles in the analyzed region. The arrows indicate the sites of the origin of the brittle fracture.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that particle failure in the in-situ test is not caused by the sample preparation. Thus, it is possible to derive reasonable information about the deformation and damage behavior of composites by surface analyses.

The deformation behavior of the investigated MMC is mainly determined by the development of particle damage. Local plastic deformation starts at pre-damaged sites of the material (i.e., fractured particles). First shear bands connect these failure sites. With increasing load, new deformation bands develop in the matrix (mostly orientated 45° to the loading axis). Further loading leads to new particle failures sites, pre-dominantly by particle fracture, which themselves lead to increased matrix deformation. Particle/matrix decohesion and void growth occurs rarely. Local matrix strains up to 8% are observed at a global strain of 1.1%.

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